

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Exploring customer perceptions on the diverse services offered by Restobar establishments

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GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 18(02), 108–119

Publication history: Received on 25 December 2023; revised on 03 February 2024; accepted on 06 February 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2024.18.2.0047>

Abstract

This study was delimited to the perceptions of customers on the different services of Restobar establishment in Northern Part of Zambales utilizing the quantitative approach and the descriptive-survey research methodology. The population of the study comprised one hundred (100) customers of Restobar and had been randomly selected.

Based on the summary of the investigations conducted, majority of respondents were females, young adulthood, single and a government employee. The respondents perceived strongly agree on consistency, courtesy, customer service, expectation, responsiveness, timeliness, and personal relationship. And perceived significant difference in consistency in terms of gender, age, and occupation; courtesy and responsiveness in terms of gender and occupation; customer service in terms of gender; expectation in terms of occupation; timeliness in terms of civil status and occupation; personal relationship in terms of civil status on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar when grouped according to profile variables.

It is highly recommended that Restobar establishments may increase their personnel consistency to assist, act and supply the needs of the visitors in a timely manner; may train/practice their employees how to listen, understand, sympathize and take action on the concerns of the visitors when a problem arises; may employees need to know what products and services they are offering when visitors ask or inquire; and a proposed plan of action may be developed by the for the improvement of guest satisfaction.

Keywords: Customer; Perception; Services; Restobar

1. Introduction

Restobar is derived from two words, restaurant and bar. A restaurant is a business establishment which prepares and serves food and drink to customers in return for money. It can be paid before the meal, after the meal or by a running tab [5]. Restobars is a crossover of a restaurant and bar. These establishments are focused on serving bar food, alcoholic beverages, and the ambiance. Restobars resemble both the characteristics of a bar and a restaurant. Restobars served a wide selection of food compared to bars which can be restricted to simple finger food. These establishments are usually themed in a way to satisfy its customers' experience. For example, there are sports restobars, Mexican restobars, and more [2].

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The counter at which drinks are served by a bartender is called the bar. It refers to a specialized counter where alcoholic drinks like beer, wine, liquor and cocktails are served and will be consumed within the premises. Prospective customers may sit or stand at the bar and be served by the bartender, or they may sit at tables and be served by cocktail servers. Bars usually have entertainment stage like live bands, acoustic artists, comedians, strippers and dancers. Bars usually with entertainment are often called music bars or night club [5].

In this study, the researchers applied a valid survey that helped determine the customers perspective on the different services of Restobar establishments in Iba, Zambales in terms of consistency, courtesy, customer service, expectation, responsiveness, timeliness, and personal relationship. The findings would be the basis for the enhancement of different Restobar services to ensure the smooth operation of the Restobar industry.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to know the customer's perspective on the different Restobar services in Iba, Zambales. It sought to answer the following questions:

- What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Gender;
 - Age;
 - Civil Status; and
 - Occupation?
- What are the perceptions of customers on the different services of Restobar in terms of:
 - Consistency;
 - Courtesy;
 - Customer Service;
 - Expectation;
 - Responsiveness;
 - Timeliness; and
 - Personal Relationship?
- Is there significant difference on the perceptions of customers on the different services of Restobar when grouped according to profile variables?

1.2. Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study was delimited to the perceptions of customers on the different services of restobar establishment in Iba, Zambales.

In this study, the data collection was conducted to select respondents from different restobar establishment in Iba, Zambales. The researchers provided a survey for the restobar that helped determine the perceived different services.

The study was conducted to perceive the customers of the different services of restobar in Iba, Zambales. The study was limited to selected restobar in San Felipe, Zambales, which was the basis for the enhancement of different restobar services to ensure the smooth operation of the restobar industry.

The researchers follow the research ethics where the names, personal data, and respondents of the respondents were held confidentially.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

The study utilized the quantitative approach and the descriptive-survey research methodology. Survey research means collecting information about a group of people by asking them questions and analyzing the results. This type of research allows for a variety of methods to recruit participants, collect data, and utilize various methods of instrumentation. Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It could answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions [6]. The descriptive survey research method was the most appropriate to use because it contains a survey and a description of facts, and the description of present situation based on age and gender. The researchers submitted the questionnaire to the research adviser and it was approved together with the panels. The gathering of the questionnaire was done after a week. After the retrieval the

result was subjected to statistics to get the frequency and percentage distribution, Weighted Mean, ANOVA test and Likert scale

2.2. Respondents and Location

The population of the study comprised the customers of each restobar in Iba, Zambales. In this study, one hundred (100) customers had been randomly selected.

The map showing the location of this study within the vicinity of Iba, Zambales is shown in figure1.

Figure 1 Locale of the Study

2.3. Research Instrument

The survey questionnaire was utilized in the study. The questionnaire was composed of two (2) parts. The first part covered the demographic profile of the respondents that includes their gender, age, civil status and occupation. The second part covered the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of restobar.

After incorporating the corrections and suggestions of the validators, the final draft was made. Furthermore, the Cronbach Alpha reliability test was administered to verify the reliability of the survey questionnaire.

Table 1 Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test

Summary of Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Restobar		
Parameters	Cronbach's Alpha based on Standardized Items	Interpretation ^b (Extent of Reliability)
Consistency	0.912	Excellent
Courtesy	0.897	Good
Customer Service	0.925	Excellent
Expectation	0.827	Good
Responsiveness	0.836	Good
Timeliness	0.820	Good
Personal Relationship	0.912	Excellent

Based on the result, the Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Restobar as to Consistency ($\alpha=0.912$), Customer Service ($\alpha=0.925$), and Personal Relationship ($\alpha=0.912$) were “Excellent”. While on Courtesy ($\alpha=0.897$), Expectation ($\alpha=0.827$), Responsiveness ($\alpha=0.836$), and Timeliness ($\alpha=0.820$) were resulted in “Good”. Thus, it is indicative that all questions can provide the necessary information to answer the objectives of the study.

2.4. Data Collection and Analysis

The survey was conducted and the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents of the research study after they have given consent to voluntarily participate in this study.

After getting the approval, the researchers sought permission from the respondents. The researchers will administer the distribution of the instrument to the respondents. The researchers will explain the objectives of the study and instruct the respondents to answer all items. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and collected after they finished accomplishing the instrument. The researchers tabulated, analysed, and interpreted the data.

Data Analysis the researchers utilized the following descriptive statistical tools:

1. Frequency (f). This statistical tool is used to calculate the number of times data has been utilized in a category. This was utilized in the profile of the respondents such as gender, age, civil status and occupation.

2. Percentage (%). This is used to determine what proportion of the respondents belongs to a specific category such as gender, age, civil status and occupation.

3. Weighted Mean. This is used to determine the customer’s perspective on the quality services of restobar establishments. For certain responses in this study, the following scale and its corresponding verbal interpretation were utilized. Verbal Interpretation these are descriptive words which give the verbal interpretation of the weighted mean.

Table 2 Verbal Interpretation of the Customers Perspective on the Different Services of Restobar Establishments

Nominal Scale	Range of Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.01-4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.01-3.00	Agree
2	1.01-2.00	Disagree
1	0.01-1.00	Strongly Disagree

4. ANOVA. To test the significance of the differences through the mean in the variables, analysis of variance (ANOVA) or F was used. It will be computed using the software SPSS. In the study, ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis regarding Ho1. There is no significant difference in the Customers Perspective on the Different Services of Restobar Establishments when grouped according to the profile variables.

Decision Rule:

Decision Rule 1. If the computed significant value is greater or higher ($>$) 0.05 Alpha level of significance, accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

Decision Rule 2. If the computed significant value is less than ($<$) 0.05 Alpha level of significance, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Profile of the Respondents

3.1.1. Gender

Out of the one hundred (100) respondents, the majority of 45 or equivalent to 45.00% were females, 42 or equivalent to 42.00% were males, and 13 or equivalent to 13.00% were members of the LGBTQ+. This implies that the most numbered guests are females who are inclined to do adventure and love to visit the restobar. Sometimes women prefer to go to the restobar to spend their free time with their friends.

3.1.2. Age

Out of the one hundred (100) respondents, the majority of 75 or equivalent to 75.00% were from between 18 – 26 years old, while only one or equivalent to 1.00% were from between 45 years old and above. The computed mean age of the respondents was 24.93 years old. This implies that most of those who go to the restobar of Iba, Zambales are in their young adulthood wherein they enjoy life while they are young.

3.1.3. Civil Status

Out of the one hundred (100) respondents, the majority of 87 or equivalent to 87.00% were singles, while only 1 or equivalent to 1.00% were widow/widower and separated, respectively. This implies that singles spend more time for themselves most especially at the restobar. In restobar and other restaurants, they are the ones who have more time to experiment.

3.1.4. Occupation

Out of the one hundred (100) respondents, the majority of 66 or equivalent to 66.00% were government employees, 31 or equivalent to 31.00% were private employees, and three or equivalent to 3.00% were others. This implies that numbered customers who frequently visit bars and restaurants are employed.

Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Restobar

3.2. Consistency

Table 3 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to consistency.

Table 3 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Consistency

	Consistency	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	All staff offer exemplified service	3.54	Strongly Agree	1
2	The staff observes the resort's uniform standards	3.52	Strongly Agree	2
3	The staff follows the time allocation in service is consistent	3.41	Strongly Agree	3
4	The staff ensures the safety of their guests during their stay	3.40	Strongly Agree	4
5	The staff delivers the same passion throughout the day.	3.30	Strongly Agree	5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.43	Strongly Agree	

The computed overall weighted mean on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to consistency was 3.43, with a qualitative interpretation of "Strongly Agree." This means that the guests were very satisfied with the consistency of restobar. The standard of expected service is most important to the safety and security of their guests as they visit which is a big reason for the guests to be loyal to them.

3.3. Courtesy

Table 4 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to courtesy.

The computed overall weighted mean on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to courtesy was 3.44, with a qualitative interpretation of “Strongly Agree.” This implies that restobar show courtesy always to the guests and do practice greetings of guests and makes them feel comfortable while they are enjoying their stay.

Table 4 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Courtesy

	Courtesy	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The staff greets the guests joyfully	3.53	Strongly Agree	1
2	The staff offers help to their guest with a willingness	3.43	Strongly Agree	3
3	The staff shows respect to their guests by handling their requests and concerns	3.46	Strongly Agree	2
4	The staff respects guest’s privacy	3.40	Strongly Agree	4.5
5	The staff welcomes inquiries from the guests	3.40	Strongly Agree	4.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.44	Strongly Agree	

3.4. Customer Service

Table 5 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to customer service.

Table 5 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Customer Service

	Customer Service	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The staff is expressing their willingness in listening to guest complaints and does quick action about it	3.54	Strongly Agree	1
2	The staff is courteous and considerate on dealing with guests	3.49	Strongly Agree	4
3	The staff does the transaction with the guests in a professional manner	3.48	Strongly Agree	5
4	The staff is willing to share information freely and open to the opinion of the guests	3.51	Strongly Agree	2
5	The staff is ready to explain to the guests that their transactions will be handled with care and quality.	3.50	Strongly Agree	3
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	Strongly Agree	

The computed overall weighted mean on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to customer service was 3.50, with a qualitative interpretation of “Strongly Agree.” This implies the guests were very satisfied on the customer service of the restobar which help them to gain loyalty of the guests. Also, the restobar are in action and easy to deal with problems that arise.

3.5. Expectation

Table 6 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to expectation.

The computed overall weighted mean on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to expectation was 3.46, with a qualitative interpretation of “Strongly Agree.” This means the restobar guests were very satisfied on what they expected. The restobar were well maintained, reliable and offers quality service.

Table 6 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Expectation

	Expectation	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The Staff is adhering to professional standards of conduct	3.60	Strongly Agree	1
2	All staff are synchronized with quality service	3.52	Strongly Agree	2
3	The Staff is well-versed in the products and services offered by the restobar	3.44	Strongly Agree	3
4	All staff are well-trained	3.34	Strongly Agree	5
5	The employees maintain the cleanliness of the restobar	3.41	Strongly Agree	4
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.46	Strongly Agree	

3.6. Responsiveness

Table 7 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to responsiveness.

The computed overall weighted mean on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to responsiveness was 3.40, with a qualitative interpretation of “Strongly Agree.”

Table 7 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Responsiveness

	Responsiveness	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The staff's willingness on doing guest requests is done promptly	3.44	Strongly Agree	2
2	The staff is attentive when it comes to guest needs and wants	3.35	Strongly Agree	5
3	The staff offers a variety of options if there is a problem with the transaction	3.40	Strongly Agree	3
4	The staff has the ability to anticipate guest's need	3.45	Strongly Agree	1
5	Staff responds abruptly to guest's requests and concerns	3.38	Strongly Agree	4
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.40	Strongly Agree	

This means that the responsiveness of the restobar was highly appreciated by the guests. Also, this emphasizes that the guests were prioritized, and accommodated to what the guests needed.

3.7. Timeliness

Table 8 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to timeliness.

This implies that guests were satisfied with the timeliness of the restobar. Most likely if the staff or personnel is attentive to what guests need and want in a timely manner.

Table 8 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Timeliness

	Timeliness	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The staff serves the guest fast and efficiently	3.46	Strongly Agree	1
2	The front desk agent gives reasonable waiting time for each transaction	3.40	Strongly Agree	4
3	The staff informs the guest of time allocation when services will be provided	3.42	Strongly Agree	2
4	The staff responds to the customer's demands in a timely manner	3.41	Strongly Agree	3
5	The staff served the food within the time frame	3.34	Strongly Agree	5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.41	Strongly Agree	

3.8. Personal Relationship

Table 9 shows the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to personal relationship.

The computed overall weighted mean on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to personal relationship was 3.47, with a qualitative interpretation of "Strongly Agree."

This implies that guests were very satisfied on the personal relationships of the restobar. It also gives information that restobar create an interactive and friendly environment as they listen to the guests for them to feel they are in good care.

Table 9 Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar as to Personal Relationship

	Personal Relationship	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The staff listens with care to the guests	3.46	Strongly Agree	4.5
2	The staff recognizes their loyal guests through their names when they encountered them inside the restobar.	3.47	Strongly Agree	2.5
3	All staffs are friendly and give a warm welcome to their loyal guest and offer a good environment during the stay	3.47	Strongly Agree	2.5
4	The staff shows concern if guests share their ideas, hope, feelings, and problems about the service of the restobar.	3.48	Strongly Agree	1
5	The staff delivers service to guests is based not just on systems, processes, and procedures but also on personal effort and creativity	3.46	Strongly Agree	4.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.47	Strongly Agree	

Test of difference on the Perceptions of the Customer-respondents on the different services of Resto Bar when grouped according to profile variables.

3.8.1. Consistency

The computed value of 0.326 for civil status was greater than $>$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to consistency when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the

computed value of 0.009 for gender, 0.030 for age and 0.022 for occupation was less than < the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to consistency when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of civil status, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to consistency are significant in terms of gender, age and occupation. Because of this, the restobar that have been open consistently meet standards.

It is important for any company providing customer service to be consistent across gender, age, and occupation. The important factor for them is to gain loyalty which requires time before they attained it from their customers. So, they will need to provide the same exact service to assure that their customers are satisfied and acquire their patronage. Furthermore, the customers are one way to market any kind of business since their experience will be the basis for service quality and market value who will deliver the information to other prospective clients in the future [7].

3.8.2. Courtesy

The computed value of 0.178 for age, and 0.479 for civil status was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to courtesy when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.025 for gender, and 0.031 for occupation was less than < the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to courtesy when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of age and civil status, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to courtesy are significant in terms of gender and occupation.

The meaning of respect and courtesy are the same and when the service staff tends to provide one of them, they will gain both from the customers and colleagues. The professional setting is where the person would need to show courtesy towards the management, other co-workers, and their clients. This enhances the satisfaction felt by all people and stakeholders because they are feeling positive vibes and goodness from the person showing these core values [4].

3.8.3. Customer Service

The computed value of 0.417 for age, 0.412 for civil status, and 0.166 for occupation was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to customer service when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.046 for gender was less than < the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to customer service when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of age, civil status and occupation, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to customer service are significant in terms of gender.

Staff members should be ready to listen to customers' problems, regardless of gender, and be able to offer solutions as part of the restobar's commitment to providing excellent customer service. Make sure that the employees know all the services offered by the restobar so that they would be able to help the guests with their requests [9].

3.8.4. Expectation

The computed value of 0.191 for gender, 0.253 for age, 0.113 for civil status, and 0.166 for occupation was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to expectation when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.012 for occupation was less than < the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to expectation when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of gender, age and civil status, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to expectation are significant in terms of occupation. The hospitality industry vowed to put their guests' needs first and to deliver quality service. Though the industry is facing a diverse number of guests, employees are expected to interact with them professionally, and with respect, and they should be responsive to the wants and needs of the guests [10].

3.8.5. Responsiveness

The computed value of 0.453 for age, and 0.130 for civil status was greater than $>$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to responsiveness when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.040 for gender, and 0.011 for occupation was less than $<$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to responsiveness when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of age and civil status, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to responsiveness are significant in terms of gender and occupation.

The study found that responsive practices among employees toward their customers will be the key to gaining satisfaction and efficient operation of any organization. It is normal to face problems and challenges, but it must resolve quickly by responding to them as soon as possible. When the customers feel that the employees are responsive, they will be satisfied because they are prioritized and accommodated immediately [8].

3.8.6. Timeliness

The computed value of 0.230 for gender, and 0.373 for age was greater than $>$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to timeliness when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.046 for civil status, and 0.022 for occupation was less than $<$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to timeliness when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of gender and age, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to timeliness are significant in terms of civil status and occupation.

To be able to provide the services in a timely manner is to increase the number of personnel to supply the needs of the customers. The customers are satisfied when the services are given to the promised time frame and would be happier if they will not wait longer. It is a fact that the success of any organization is to achieve the satisfaction of their customers. They will need to compromise their products and services to assure that the needs and preference of the clients are attained [1].

3.8.7. Personal Relationship

The computed value of 0.365 for gender, 0.163 for age, and 0.071 for occupation was greater than $>$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to personal relationship when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.011 for civil status was less than $<$ the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to personal relationship when grouped according to profile variables.

The results revealed that, regardless of gender, age and occupation, the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar as to timeliness are significant in terms of civil status.

The personal relationship between employees and their customers has a high impact on customer loyalty. The personal relationship may build friendships that would encourage customers to return and acquire the same services because they personally know the employees [3].

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the summary of the investigations conducted, the researchers have concluded that:

- The majority of respondents were females, aged between 18-26, single and a government employee.
- The respondents perceived “Strongly Agree” on consistency, courtesy, customer service, expectation, responsiveness, timeliness, and personal relationship on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar with a computed overall grand mean of 3.44.
- The respondents perceived no significant difference in consistency in terms of civil status, courtesy and responsiveness in terms of age and civil status, customer service in terms of age, civil status, and occupation, expectation in terms of gender, age, and civil status, timeliness in terms of gender, and age, and personal relationship in terms of gender, age, and occupation on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the respondents assessed significant difference in consistency in terms of gender, age, and occupation, courtesy and responsiveness in terms of gender and occupation, customer service in terms of gender, expectation in terms of occupation, timeliness in terms of civil status, and occupation, and personal relationship in terms of civil status on the perceptions of the customer-respondents on the different services of resto bar when grouped according to profile variables.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are as follows:

- The restobar establishments should increase their personnel consistency to assist, act and supply the needs of the visitors in a timely manner.
- The restobar establishments should train/practice their employees how to listen, understand, sympathize and take action on the concerns of the visitors when a problem arises.
- The restobar establishments employees should know what products and services they are offering when visitors ask or inquire.
- A proposed plan of action may be developed by the restobar establishments t for the improvement of guest satisfaction.
- Parallel study shall also be conducted using different settings, respondents, and variables to validate the findings of this research study.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

The author would like to express his gratitude to all individuals and organizations who provided support and assistance in conducting this research study. This includes the participants who willingly shared their time and experiences, as well as the organizations that allowed access to their facilities and resources. The author would also like to acknowledge the guidance and expertise provided by their research advisers, as well as the support and encouragement from their colleagues and loved ones throughout the duration of this study.

All the authors of must disclose the possible conflicts of interest/ Competing Interests they may have with publication of the manuscript or an institution or product that is mentioned in the manuscript and/or is important to the outcome of the study presented. Authors should also disclose conflict of interest with products that compete with those mentioned in their manuscript.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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